

WHAT MAKES A RESIDENTIAL BUILDING GREEN AND BARRIERS TO ITS ADAPTION: A REAL ESTATE DEVELOPERS PERSPECTIVE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is understanding the developer's perspective on the key features of a green residential building for which a buyer is willing to pay premium price and to examine the barriers that restrict developers in its adaption. For this purpose, a comprehensive questionnaire was developed and the data was collected through survey. Based on 55 responses, the relative importance index for features of a green building and the barriers to its implementation was calculated. These barriers and features were also grouped using exploratory factor analysis. The results suggested that according to a developer, the essential features of a green building are environmentally appropriate site; where water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period; which saves energy, and has a sound storm water management system and uses of high albedo roofing material. On the other side, lack of knowledge among stakeholders; buyers do not want to pay extra (premium pricing), affordability and lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies are the major barriers to its adaption.

Keywords: Green Building, Residential, Developers, Barriers, Sustainability.

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I. INTRODUCTION

With a total population of more than 1.3 billion, India is the most populated country in the world. As a result, the demand for residential buildings is increasing (Shah, 2018). This demand is further fuelled by the rapid movement of rural population towards urban cities. It is estimated that about 600 million people would be living in Indian cities by 2036 (Athar et al., 2022).

According to a World Bank report, India needs to invest \$840 billion over the next 15 years (an average of \$55 billion per annum) into urban infrastructure if it is to effectively meet the needs of its fast-growing urban population. This massive investment would make the market Indian real estate sector as the largest contributor to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the Indian real estate sector will reach a market size of \$1Trillion by 2030 (Indian Brand Equity Foundation (2019). This presents tremendous opportunities for the domestic and international players in the real estate market called “Developers” henceforth.

The developers in order to exploit the opportunities are working fast and creating a lot of urban infrastructure across the globe, particularly in emerging economies like India. However, this rapid urbanization is disturbing the natural balance between people and planet through exploitation of resources and harming the environment. It is noted that the buildings (residential and non-residential) accounts for one-sixth of the world’s freshwater withdrawals, one quarter of the wood harvested and two-fifths of its materials, which indicates its intensive resource consumption (Deng, Li, & Quigley, 2012). The construction and operation of buildings account for about forty percent of worldwide consumption of raw materials and energy. Buildings and their associated construction activities account for almost a third of world greenhouse gas emissions. (Deng, Li, & Quigley, 2012; Guggemos and Horvath, 2005). Thus, small increases in the “sustainability” of buildings, or more specifically in the energy efficiency of their construction, can have large effects on their current use of energy and on their life-cycle energy consumption. Hence, as projected (Costa and Kahn, 2009; Davis, 2009; Zheng et al., 2009, 2011), the importance of energy efficiency in building has increased, dramatically over the last decade.

There is a growing awareness amongst developers about the potential of sustainable construction to positively affect environmental issues. This has pushed green building to the forefront (Abidin et al., 2013) and sustainability has become a key word. Since, the design and operation of a building can play an important role in energy conservation in advanced societies (Eichholtz, Kok, & Quigley, 2010), therefore, in recent years, green building concept and energy-saving tips, and tools to evaluate and compare buildings and their sustainable features have been introduced to the real estate market. The same can be seen from the surge of building rating systems initiated by both government and industry around the globe and certification of sustainable buildings has become common in many countries (Falkenbach et al., 2010).

1.1. Defining Green Building

World Green Building Council (WGBC) defines a green building as “a building that, in its design, construction or operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and creates positive impacts, on our climate and natural environment.”. Similarly, Abidin et al. (2013) said that a building that decreases energy demand, reduce cost, and improve health and productivity of employees can be considered as green. “A green building or sustainable building is defined as one, which uses less water, optimises energy efficiency, conserves natural resources, generates less waste and provides healthier spaces for occupants, as compared to a conventional building (Manna and Banerjee, 2019)”. Table I presents a brief summary of the key features that several green building rating systems across the world use as assessment criteria.

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Table I: Green Building Rating Systems

S. No.	System	Assessment Criteria
1	Singapore Green Mark program (GM)	Which evaluates buildings for their environmental impact and energy performance (Deng, Li, & Quigley, 2012)
2	Energy Star	Which reduce greenhouse gas emissions and other pollutants caused by the inefficient use of energy; and make it easy for consumers to identify and purchase energy-efficient products that offer savings on energy bills without sacrificing performance, features, and comfort. (Devine, A., & Kok, N., 2015).
3	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased energy savings • Efficient use of water • Reduced greenhouse gas emissions • Healthier indoor air quality • Increased use of recycled materials • Optimum utilization of resources • Location and transportation • Sustainable sites • Innovation • Reduced costs of operation and maintenance
4	Ecology, energy saving, waste reduction, and health (EEWH) system Taiwan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity • Greenery • Soil water retention • Daily energy conservation • More economical building materials used during construction • Construction waste reduction • Indoor environment quality • Water conservation • The focus of improving sewage and garbage disposal (Fong-Yao, Jen-Hsu and Michael, 2022)
5	IGBC (Indian Green Building Council)	Which uses less energy, water and other natural resources, creates less waste & Green House Gases and is healthy for people during living or working inside as compared to a standard Building

Source: Authors Compilation

Typically, if we look at the assessment criteria of any green building certificate, it covers the following key areas:

- Energy Efficiency
- Water Efficiency
- Environmental Protection
- Indoor Environmental Quality
- Other Green Features and Innovation

1.2. Green Building Movement in India

Urban growth is a global phenomenon that has resulted from intense human activities and development. India being the most populous country in the world, is also witnessing mass urbanization. This urbanization led to rapid economic development in India, however, climate change due to greenhouse gas emissions, energy security and accessibility have been identified as major concerns for urbanization in India (Thanu and Rajasekaran, 2018). Hence, to address this concern and to maintain the spirit of 'Our Common Future' (WCED, 1987), the Green Building Movement was adopted in India by the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII) in 2001 (Manna & Banerjee, 2019). CII formed the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC) which is actively involved in promoting the Green Building concept in India. Their vision is to enable a sustainable built environment for all and facilitate India to be one of the global leaders in the sustainable built environment by 2025. India has two major green building certification agencies: LEED India is by the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC) and Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment (GRIHA), formulated by The Energy Research Institute (TERI). These certifications aim to regulate the infrastructure and promote sustainable building practices to preserve urban ecology. Their application is closely linked with the building bylaws of the State and Central Government in India (Singh and Raghubanshi, 2020).

1.3. Green Buildings and Pricing Dilemma for Developer

Studies in the past have examined the relationship between green buildings and pricing presenting a mixed result. Fuerst & McAllister, (2011) and Eichholtz, Kok, & Quigley (2010) investigated green label in affecting the market rents and values of commercial space in USA and found that identical commercial building with an Energy Star certification will rent for about 3 percent more per square foot. Similarly, Deng, Li & Quigley (2012) examined the building projects in the City of Singapore that have been awarded the Green Mark for energy efficiency and sustainability and found a significant premium in selling prices for dwellings with Green Mark Certification. However, the premiums noticed by Eichholtz, Kok, & Quigley (2010) started to diminish by 2013 (Eichholtz, Kok, & Quigley, 2013). Dwaikat and Ali, (2016) analysed cost premiums associated with green buildings compared to conventional buildings but found no consensus. Similarly, Fong-Yao, Jen-Hsu and Michael (2022) noted that buyers are not willing to pay higher prices for all the green building features in Taiwan. Thus, the developers are willing to invest in these green building features for which buyers are willing to pay higher prices.

Further, it is argued that green building premium, if any, may not be available immediately at the time of sale of the unit to the developer (Deng & Wu, 2014). According to Deng & Wu (2014), in the residential sector, particularly in Asian markets, dwelling units are always sold to households immediately after they have been completed or in fact, may be presold before they have been completed. This way, the developers get the opportunity to collect the price of the building just at the beginning of construction. This mechanism works well in the markets which do not exhibit information asymmetry.

However, country like India, where information asymmetry is very high between the buyer and the developer, the green price premium is only fully revealed in the market after the units are already sold to households. As a result, the developers extract a very small portion of the benefits associated with their energy-efficiency investments, while they still have to pay almost all the costs of such investments during the construction (Deng, & Wu, 2014). Thus, even if a price premium for green dwelling units does exist in the market, its existence might not lead to developers obtaining any meaningful economic returns.

This situation presents a dilemma for the developer as to which are those features for which the buyer is willing to pay premium. Further, the dilemma continues because the developer may also be constrained by other factors (lack of technological know-how, lack of awareness among various stakeholders, cost of adoption of sustainable residential green buildings, and lack of government incentive). Having too many rating agencies throwing different assessment criteria also adds to the confusion for the developer (Falkenbach et al., 2010). Therefore, a developer may not commit to all the features of a green building recommended by a certification agency and identification of those features for which the buyer is willing to pay a premium becomes paramount for the developer.

However, the common question addressed in the existing literature is how “green” certification of properties is related to cash flows and property valuations & pricing, and generally the evidence shows positive financial effects associated with better environmental performance (Eichholtz, Kok & Yonder, 2012). Studies in the past have not tried to understand the developer’s perspective on the key features of a green residential building desired by a buyer and the barriers that restrict than in its adaption. The present study is an attempt in this direction. The study attempts to understand developer’s perspective on the key features of a green residential building for which buyer is willing to pay premium price and the barriers that restrict than in its adaption, particularly in India. The choice of India is driven by multiple factors such as:

- A. India exhibits very high information asymmetry between the developer and the buyer. This makes India as most suitable geography to carry out this study.
- B. Due to mass urbanization and rapid movement of rural population to Tier 1 and Teir II cities, the developers with high rise colonies are growing rapidly in all parts of the country. If these developers can be attracted and moulded with the help of some incentives and mandatory provisions in the building bylaws to adopt green building concepts in their projects, it will help reduce carbon emission (Singh and Raghubanshi, 2020).
- C. According to Indian Brand Equity Foundation (2019), the Indian real estate sector is expected to reach a market size of \$1 Trillion by 2030 making is one of the fastest growing sectors in India.

The rest of the study is divided in 5 sections. The next section is literature review followed by research methodology, data analysis, discussion on results and conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

World over, the scholars have examined the features that make a building sustainable and the barriers to its adaption. In an early study, Hoffman and Henn, (2008) discussed the slow adoption of green building practices in the design and construction industry despite the availability of cost-effective products and services. They identified social and psychological barriers at individual, organizational, and institutional level that hinder the progress of environmental sustainability in building design and delivery and concluded with seven strategies for overcoming these barriers, including issue framing, education, structural and incentive change, indemnifying risk, a green building standard improvement, targeting the right demographic, and tax reform. Pitt et al. (2009) attempted to work on understanding the factors that promote or prevent sustainable construction practices and establishing consistency in how sustainability is measured. The study found that fiscal incentives/penalties and regulations help to drive sustainable construction, and affordability is the biggest barrier. Similarly, Winston, (2010) attempted to assess housing and regeneration in Dublin since the early 1980s and identifies barriers to achieving sustainable housing, such as inadequate building regulations, negative attitudes towards social mix, and limited resources.

The study concluded that it is essential to target resources at enforcing building regulations, providing sufficient social and affordable housing, and retrofitting unsustainable housing constructed in the past. Alias et al. (2010) focusing on the concept of green homes in Malaysia found that uncertainty about people's acceptability towards green homes and the price are the biggest problems faced by developers when developing green homes. Falkenbach et al., (2010) focused on the drivers of environmental sustainability in the real estate market.

The case study of Finland (Häkkinen and Belloni, 2011) found that sustainable buildings are not hindered by a lack of technologies and assessment methods but is instead beset with organizational and procedural difficulties entailed by the adoption of new methods. The barriers are outlined as steering mechanisms, economics, a lack of client understanding, process (procurement and tendering, timing, cooperation, and networking), and underpinning knowledge (knowledge and common language, the availability of methods and tools, innovation). The most important actions to promote sustainable building are the development of the awareness of clients about the benefits of sustainable building, the development and adoption of methods for sustainable building requirement management, the mobilization of sustainable building tools, the development of designers' competence and team working, and the development of new concepts and services.

In another study in Malaysia, (Abidin et al., 2013) found that technological advancements, institutional support, internal action, and market influence are the enablers of green buildings and the lack of incentive programs and slow progress in revising regulations for institutional support, the cost of importing green technology for technological advancements, the cost factor and lack of urgency for internal action, and low demand from potential buyers for market influence are the major barriers. Du et al. (2014) their study in China identified fifteen barriers that are divided into five groups based on factor analysis. The barriers related to profitability hamper the adoption of these technologies.

Nguyen et al. (2017) examined the barriers to green building adoption in Vietnam and identified 41 barriers across four categories: legislative and institutional barriers; technical and financial barriers; social and cognitive barriers; and market and demand barriers. Darko et al. (2017) presented a classification framework for the drivers, which includes five main categories: external drivers, corporate-level drivers, property-level drivers, project-level drivers, and individual-level drivers.

Darko et al. (2018) investigated the factors that influence the adoption of green building technologies in Ghana and provided useful insights. Abraham and HariPriya (2018) in a study in India identified 20 specific barriers classified into four categories: Policy and Market Barriers, Financial and Economic Barriers, Information, Promotion and Education Barriers, and Managerial and Organizational Barriers. The study identifies lack of expertise in life-cycle cost, lack of information on benefits of green buildings, lack of labelling lack of infrastructure and training, weak enforcement of building codes, absence of incentives, and high capital costs as the top seven specific barriers. In a similar study Luthra et al. (2015) discussed the barriers to the adoption of renewable and sustainable energy technologies in India and identified 28 barriers and categorizes them into seven dimensions, including economical and financial, market, awareness, and information, technical, ecological, and geographical, cultural, behavioural, and political and government issues.

Nikyema and Blouin (2020) discussed the barriers to implement green design and green materials in developing countries and identified five types of barriers: government, humans, knowledge and information, market, and cost and risk. Saha et al. (2021) discussed the barriers to the adoption of green buildings in the Commercial Green Buildings and classified the barriers into economic, governmental, organizational, and social perception, information, technology, and material categories.

Li et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis proposed future research directions, including extending studies to cover all green building stakeholders, more emphasis on operation and demolition stages, more investigation on green commercial buildings, and more studies on innovative research methods.

Overall, the literature review revealed that sustainable construction in residential buildings is an emerging domain and scholars are identifying its drivers and barriers to implementation. The domain is getting richer with each piece of paper and the current study is an attempt to add to the existing and growing body of knowledge.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Questionnaire Development

The aim of this study is understanding the developer's perspective on the key features of a green residential building for which a buyer is willing to pay premium price and to examine the barriers that restrict developers in its adaption. For this purpose, author carried out literature review and identified a list of 15 features and 16 barriers. The list was cross validated through two industry experts who have a work experience of more than 25 years in the real estate market in India. The list of features includes items such as environmentally appropriate site, water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period, saves energy, has a sound storm water management system, uses of high albedo roofing material, uses plants, soils, microbes, and engineered systems like underground detention tanks, promotes and restores surrounding habitats, has shading to avoid heat Island effect, uses renewable energy to reduce greenhouse gases, conserve existing natural areas, reduces harmful environmental effect during only the construction period, reduces harmful environmental effect during the entire life cycle of the building, minimizes water wastage and increasing recycling methods by installing mechanisms throughout the building life cycle, minimizes water wastage during construction, promote reduce, reuse and recycle. All these items are highly relevant in Indian context as India is geographically a very diverse country. Certain parts of the country are extremely hot and the temperature reaches 45 degree calculous in summer (Delhi, Agra, Jaipur), whereas some coastal like Mumbai and Chennai are hot and humid.

The barriers such as lack of knowledge among stakeholders, buyers do not want to pay extra (Premium Pricing), affordability, lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies, lack of incentives, lack of Government Support, complex certification procedures for subsidies and tax concessions, lack of importance attached by top leaders of enterprises, lack of professionalism, lack of willingness, lack of techniques and tools for estimation of saved energy, imperfect testing standards for saving energy, not possible to verify the quality of product even though it meets the sustainable building requirements, lack of demand, unsuitable law and regulations and sustainable buildings solutions may have unknown risk for which designers might held be accountable are also highly to all the stakeholders in India.

Since, the study is carried out form the developer's perspective, the questionnaire was sent to real estate developers. The questionnaire was developed on Likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 meant least important feature and 5 meant most important feature. For barriers, 1 meant not a barrier at all and 5 meant a very strong barrier.

3.2. Data Collection Process

Owing to the unique and scarce nature of the study, a non-probabilistic snowball sampling method was adopted to reach the potential respondents. Snowball sampling is a commonly employed sampling method in qualitative research, used in medical science and in various social sciences, including sociology, political science, anthropology and human geography (Noy, 2009). It is very difficult to have magical start, proceed and terminate for snowball sampling (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981) because the technique attempts to develop a diverse sample through continuous and deliberate effort. The sampling creates a social network and the respondents are approached. This approach towards data collection has precedence in Prakash and Phadtare (2018) and Rastogi and Singla (2022).

Author in this study had the advantage of working with the premier institute in the field of construction and real estate management in India. Hence, the initial survey form was sent to its alumni who are developers. Further, the developer's directories were used taking help of The Confederation of Real Estate Developers' Associations of India (CREDAI). CREDAI is the apex body of private Real Estate developers in India, established in 1999, with a vision of transforming the landscape of Indian Real Estate industry and a mandate to pursue the cause of Housing and Habitat. Today, CREDAI represents 13000+ Developers across 230 city chapters in 21 states and plays an important role in policy formulation by representing the views of its members to various ministries at regular intervals. Thereafter, social network of those developers was developed to reach out to a greater number of people. The survey was kept open for a period of two months between February and March 2023.

3.3. Sample Filtering and Profile

Despite efforts, only 63 completed responses were received during the data collection period. To examine the level of consistency in responses, intraindividual response variability (IRV) was calculated. It is the within-person standard deviation of the raw scores (Dunn et al., 2018; Hong et al. 2020). An IRV value below 0.50 indicates that responses lack variability. We found eight such respondents, whose responses were eliminated. Accordingly, 55 valid responses were used for data analyses. A brief Profile of respondents is shown in Table II. Most of the respondents are male and are in the aged below 40.

Table II: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Gender	Nos	%
<i>Male</i>	41	74.55%
<i>Female</i>	14	25.45%
Total Experience		
<i>5 to 10 years</i>	16	29.09%
<i>10 to 20 years</i>	29	52.73%
<i>More than 20 years</i>	10	18.18%
Age		
<i>31-40</i>	23	41.82%
<i>41-50</i>	22	40.00%
<i>51 and above</i>	10	18.18%

Source: Authors Compilation

3.4. Method of Analysis

Firstly, the data was analysed using relative importance index (RII). Survey data in construction management research are frequently analysed using the RII method. Researchers (Assaf et al., 1995; Faridi and El-Sayegh, 2006; Iyer and Jha 2005) have found RII as an effective method and argued about its use and commented on its suitability over mean and standard deviation for ranking of attributes.

Secondly, the barriers and the features were grouped using exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a statistical approach that can be used to analyse interrelationships among many variables and to explain these variables in terms of their common underlying dimensions (factors). The objective of EFA is to find a way of condensing the information contained in several original variables into a smaller set of factors with minimum loss of information (Hair et al., 2010).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. RELATIVE IMPORTANCE INDEX

Relative Importance Index (RII) is a non-parametric technique widely used by construction and facilities management researchers for analysing structured questionnaire responses for data involving ordinal measurement of attitudes.

$$RII = \Sigma W / (A * N)$$

Where, W is the weighting given to each factor by the respondents (ranging from 1 to 5), A is the highest weight (i.e., 5 in this case), and N is the total number of respondents. Higher the value of RII, more important was the feature and barrier.

Table III provides the RII for the features that are required to make a residential building sustainable, and Table IV provides the RII for the barriers to adaption of sustainable residential buildings.

Table III: Essential Features for a Sustainable Residential Building

S. No.	Essential Features for a Sustainable Residential Building	RII	Rank
1	Environmentally appropriate site	3.88	1
2	Water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period	3.88	1
3	Saves energy	3.76	3
4	Has a sound storm water management system	3.67	4
5	Uses of high albedo roofing material	3.65	5
6	Uses plants, soils, microbes, and engineered systems like underground detention tanks	3.47	6
7	Promotes and restores surrounding habitats	3.39	7
8	Has shading to avoid Heat Island Effect	3.39	7
9	Uses renewable energy to reduce greenhouse gases	3.37	9
10	Conserve existing natural areas	3.35	10
11	Reduces harmful environmental effect during only the construction period	3.25	11
12	Reduces harmful environmental effect during the entire life cycle of the building	3.25	11
13	Minimizes water wastage and increasing recycling methods by installing mechanisms throughout the building life cycle	3.18	13
14	Minimizes water wastage during construction	3.14	14
15	Promote Reduce, Reuse and Recycle	3.02	15

Source: Authors Compilation

Table III shows that the top five features are environmentally appropriate site; water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period; saves energy; has a sound storm water management system and uses of high albedo roofing material. These are the top features for which a buyer is willing to pay. Results in Table IV reveal that lack of knowledge among stakeholders, buyers do not want to pay extra for sustainable buildings requirements, premium pricing, affordability and lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies are the major barriers to adaption of sustainable residential buildings in India.

Table IV: Barriers to Sustainable Residential Building

S. No.	Barriers to Sustainable Residential Building	RII	Rank
1	Lack of knowledge among stakeholders	3.84	1
2	Buyers do not want to pay extra (Premium Pricing)	3.80	2
3	Affordability	3.64	3
4	Lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies	3.60	4
5	Lack of Incentives	3.44	5
6	Lack of Government Support	3.40	6
7	Complex certification procedures for subsidies and tax concessions	3.38	7
8	Lack of importance attached by top leaders of enterprises	3.38	8
9	Lack of Professionalism	3.36	8
10	Lack of Willingness	3.35	10
11	Lack of techniques and tools for estimation of saved energy	3.22	11
12	Imperfect testing standards for saving energy	3.20	12
13	Not possible to verify the quality of product even though it meets the SB requirements	3.16	13
14	Lack of Demand	3.15	14
15	Unsuitable law and regulations	3.02	15
16	Sustainable Buildings solutions may have unknown risk for which designers might held be accountable	2.87	16

Source: Authors Compilation

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analyses for Features of Green Building and Barriers

4.2.1. Prerequisites

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure (KMO) test and Bartlett's test of sphericity are prerequisites to EFA and indicate the suitability of dataset for performing EFA (Hair et al., 2010). A KMO value above 0.6 is desirable, however, our KMO test resulted in a value of 0.825 for features and 0.828 for the barriers, indicating excellent sampling adequacy. Further, Bartlett's test of sphericity was found to be significant for both sets (For Features chi-square value of 485.291, $df = 105$ and for Barrier's chi-square value of 514.745 with $df = 55$) rejecting the null hypothesis of that the variables are not correlated. The values of measures of sampling adequacy (MSA) and communalities were also well above the cut off 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010). As our data met the prerequisites of exploratory factor analysis (EFA), we performed EFA in an iterative manner, until we arrived at a clean matrix with factor loadings.

4.2.2. Factors Extraction for Features of Green Building

We found two factors based on the decision criterion of Eigen value greater than ($>$) 1 (Hair et al., 2010) for features of green building. The extraction method used was principal component analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation. The factor loading cut off considered was 0.50, which is appropriate for sample size of below 100 (Hair et al., 2010).

Table V and Table VI represent the results of EFA of Features and Barriers, respectively.

Table V: Results of EFA for Features of Sustainable Residential Buildings

Item	MSA	Communalities	Loadings	% Variance Explained	Cronbach's Alpha
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period 	0.803	0.605	0.769	41.772	0.929
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimizes water wastage during construction 	0.756	0.715	0.795		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimizes water wastage and increasing recycling methods by installing mechanisms throughout the building life cycle 	0.852	0.789	0.83		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Reduce, Reuse and Recycle 	0.786	0.711	0.789		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses renewable energy to reduce greenhouse gases 	0.869	0.814	0.79		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduces harmful environmental effect during the entire life cycle of the building 	0.896	0.831	0.829		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conserve existing natural areas 	0.854	0.678	0.685	30.354	0.868
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has a sound storm water management system 	0.889	0.611	0.61		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses plants, soils, microbes, and engineered systems like underground detention tanks 	0.838	0.757	0.74		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses of high albedo roofing material 	0.757	0.753	0.819		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduces harmful environmental effect during only the construction period 	0.768	0.665	0.812		

Source: Authors Compilation

In Table V there were 15 items out of which 11 are retained. The other four items were dropped due to cross-loadings. The first factor consist of items like water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period; minimizes water wastage during construction; minimizes water wastage and increasing recycling methods by installing mechanisms throughout the building life cycle; promote reduce, reuse and recycle, uses renewable energy to reduce greenhouse gases and reduces harmful environmental effect during the entire life cycle of the building. Hence, it was named as “Waste Management and Environment Friendly Buildings (WMEFB)”. The WMEFB explained 41.77% of the variance. The second factor consist items like conserve existing natural areas; has a sound storm water management system; uses plants, soils, microbes, and engineered systems like underground detention tanks; uses of high albedo roofing material; reduces harmful environmental effect during only the construction period. This factor was named as “Resources Conserving Building (RCB)”. It explained 30.35% of the variance. After extracting these two constructs, their reliability is assessed. Cronbach’s alpha is a measure of assessing the reliability of constructs by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. For an instrument to be reliable, there should be a greater covariance among the items relative to the variance (Collins, 2007). The Cronbach’s alpha for WMEFB is 0.929 and for RCB is 0.868. Thus, Cronbach’s alpha was found to be excellent both the factors (Hair et al., 2010).

4.2.3. Factors Extraction for Barriers to Adaption of Green Building

In Table VI there were 16 items out of which 15 are retained after EFA. One item was dropped because of cross-loadings. The barriers to residential green buildings led to four constructs namely lack of system support (SU-SYS), lack of internal support (INT_SY), high cost (COST_ST) and others (OTHER). SU-SYS explained 25.67% of the variance, INT_SY explained 18.35% variance, COST_ST explained 14.98% variance whereas OTHER explained 14.13% of the variance. The Cronbach’s alpha values for SU_SYS, INT_SY, COST_ST and OTHER were respectively 0.908, 0.814, 0.792 and 0.801. Thus, reliability was found to be excellent (Hair et al., 2010).

Table VI: Results of EFA for Barriers of Adoption of Green Buildings

Item	Communalities	MSA	Loadings	% Variance Explained	Cronbach's Alpha
• Lack of Government Support	0.688	0.810	0.670	25.677	0.908
• Unsuitable law and regulations	0.817	0.828	0.782		
• Imperfect testing standards for saving energy	0.798	0.804	0.774		
• Lack of techniques and tools for estimation of saved energy	0.762	0.818	0.772		
• Lack of importance attached by top leaders of enterprises	0.636	0.863	0.637		
• Sustainable Buildings solutions may have unknown risk for which designers might held be accountable	0.602	0.940	0.737		

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• Lack of knowledge among stakeholders	0.711	0.826	0.804		
• Lack of Willingness	0.771	0.660	0.755		
• Lack of Professionalism	0.597	0.823	0.590		
• Lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies	0.690	0.828	0.617	18.354	0.814
• Buyers do not want to pay extra (Premium Pricing)	0.869	0.689	0.906	14.981	0.792
• Affordability	0.816	0.804	0.814		
• Lack of Incentives	0.711	0.870	0.520		
• Lack of Demand	0.8	0.807	0.791	14.138	0.801
• Not possible to verify the quality of product even though it meets the sustainable building requirements	0.744	0.800	0.760		

Source: Authors Compilation, Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis, Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization, Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

5. DISCUSSION ON RESULTS

The study sought to examine the understanding the developer's perspective on the key features of a green residential building for which a buyer is willing to pay premium price and to examine the barriers that restrict developers in its adaption. As noted by Fong-Yao, Jen-Hsu and Michael (2022) buyers are not willing to pay higher prices for all the green building features. Thus, the developers are willing to invest in these green building features for which buyers are willing to pay higher prices. Towards this objective a questionnaire survey was carried out and the features of a green residential buildings and barriers to its adaption were ranked using RII technique. It is found that a building that has environmentally appropriate site; where water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period, which saves energy, and has a sound storm water management system and uses of high albedo roofing material are considered green by developers in India. On the other side, lack of knowledge among stakeholders, buyers do not want to pay extra, affordability (Hoffman and Henn, 2008; Pitt et al., 2009) and lack of access of information on cost and benefits of using energy saving technologies are the major barriers to adaption of the concept of sustainable residential buildings. Further, authors grouped the features of a sustainable residential building into two categories namely Waste Management and Environment Friendly Buildings (WMEFB) and Resources Conserving Building (RCB) and the barriers were grouped into four categories namely system support (SU_SYS), internal support (INT_SY), Cost (COST_ST) and Other (OTHER). These results are in line with the extant research particularly like the one by Pitt et al. (2009), Nguyen et al. (2017), Darko et al. (2017), Darko et al. (2018), Abraham and Haripriya (2018) and Alias et al. (2010).

6. CONCLUSION

In the context of climate change, sustainable building plays a vital role in reducing carbon footprint and slowing the rate of global warming. The building sector is responsible for a sizeable portion of the world's energy consumption and carbon emissions. By designing, constructing, and operating sustainable buildings, we can reduce the carbon emissions associated with the built environment and help mitigate the effects of climate change.

India has undertaken diverse initiatives to address the threat of climate change. The findings of the study once again confirm the need for government actions to overcome these challenges and push towards sustainable residential buildings.

6.1. Implications for stakeholders

The study findings have implications for developers as well as for government agencies. Finding an appropriate value for a property is always a challenge for the developer. This study finds that according to developer a buyer is willing to pay premium price for green features like environmentally appropriate site, a site where water is harvested, used, purified, reused during entire construction period, which saves energy, has a sound storm water management system, uses of high albedo roofing material, uses plants, soils, microbes, and engineered systems like underground detention tanks, promotes and restores surrounding habitats and has shading to avoid heat Island effect. Hence, developers must ensure that these features are provided in their building to attract premium pricing as well as attain sustainability agenda. However, lack of support, especially from the external agencies is the major barrier towards adaption of sustainable residential buildings in India. It is advised that government must provide adequate financial support to introduce these features in buildings. It is well known that the initial cost for a sustainable building is too high. The consumers are not willing to bear that cost, and the developers are not able to absorb that cost. Hence, it is recommended that government provides necessary support to the developers in form of incentives and subsidies. Further, both government and developers must look to educate people and create sensitivity towards sustainable residential buildings.

6.2. Limitation and Scope for future work

The study is not without limitations. Primarily, due to the nature of study, the sample size is small. Hence, it is difficult to generalize the findings of the study. Further, the study has been carried from the developer's perspective. However, despite these limitations, the study does provide significant information and adds to the growing body of knowledge in the field of green residential buildings. It is not possible for developers in emerging economies to invest in the green buildings and absorb the cost. Hence, if the nations want to achieve sustainable buildings and reduce carbon emission, such studies are needed in different geographical context. It will help developers to focus on the key features of green building for which a buyer is aware and willing to pay.

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